

Advanced collision avoidance architecture for the MORFEO LOR WFS: integrating software, electrical, and mechanical protections

Tommaso Lapucci^a, Dheeraj Malik^a, Edoardo Maria Redaelli^b, Fulvio Laudisio^c, Bernardo Salasnich^c, Lorenzo Busoni^a, Marco Bonaglia^a.

^aInaf Arcetri, Largo Enrico fermi 5, Florence, Italy; Inaf Merate^b, Via E. Bianchi 46, Merate, Italy, Inaf Padova^b, Via dell'Osservatorio 5, Padova, Italy

ABSTRACT

The Low Order and Reference (LOR) Module provides Natural Guide Star (NGS) wavefront sensing capabilities for MORFEO in Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics (MCAO) mode. The module includes three identical units, each designed to detect wavefront aberrations from one of three NGSs selected within a technical field having an outer radius of 80". Each LOR WFS unit patrols approximately half of this field using motorized XY stages to cover their portion of the technical field, equivalent to 540 x 270 mm given the nominal plate-scale in the LOR focal plane of 3.315 mm/arcsec. The three WFS units are mounted on a common support structure with a 120° geometry and the three units can move within overlapping areas. To avoid mechanical interference and collision, the system includes an anti-collision architecture that is described in this paper. The strategy relies on two complementary layers. The first is the Anti-Collision Software (ACS), implemented at the low-level TwinCAT software running on the instrument PLC. By continuously monitoring the positions of the stages of all LOR WFS units in real time with a PLC cycle time of 1 ms, the PLC software will acquire the values coming from the absolute encoders and execute only allowed trajectories depending on the current position of each motor. The second layer, the Stop-upon Collision System (SCS), provides hardware-level protection. It uses conductive tapes as contact sensors, mechanical joints to protect hardware during impact, and control electronics that instantly cut power to the actuators in case of contact. This protection layer will allow halting motion and avoiding mechanical damage in case of an error in the ACS software.

Keywords: MORFEO, NGS MCAO, PLC, Electronics, Software

1. INTRODUCTION

The MORFEO LOR WFS are designed to acquire the NGS within a technical field of 160 arcsec diameter. MORFEO comprises three LOR WFS units, which are mounted on a common support structure in a 120° geometric configuration. Each WFS can acquire its NGS by means of Acquisition Stages (AST), which consist of orthogonal linear actuators able to move each unit in an area of 300x600 mm², as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of the LOR support structure attached to the MICADO central flange. The three LOR WFS Units are supported on top of their Acquisition Stages

The stages selected to implement the NGS acquisition functionality of the LOR WFS are the Physik Instrumente LS-270 and LS-180 with minor modifications to the travel range of LS-270 and absolute linear encoders with a resolution of 1nm on both axes to compute the position of LOR WFS boards in real time. Additionally, the stages are fitted with 5:1 gear reductions and larger stepper motors compared to their commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) versions. These modifications and precautions taken for the ASTs ensure that the assembly will move very little ($\ll 10$ mm) during the given earthquake conditions. In addition to seismic risk, the MORFEO configuration presents a potential collision hazard between LOR WFS boards due to their overlapping operational areas during the NGS acquiring stage as shown in fig 2.

Figure 2. The figure shows the areas patrolled by the 3 LOR WFS units in blue, green and red areas. The cyan, orange and violet areas represent the areas that may be occupied by 2 POMs at the same time and hence where collision may occur.

Managing moving hardware components is a common challenge in telescope instruments, and different countermeasures can be applied depending on the specific operational context to minimize the risk of collisions and mechanical failures. Anti-collision systems have therefore become increasingly important in modern astronomical instrumentation, where multiple actuated subsystems operate safely in crowded spaces. For example, the Infrared Imaging Spectrograph (IRIS) for the Thirty Meter Telescope, the on-instrument wavefront sensor (OIWFS) probe arms rely on a motion-planning approach that predicts their paths in advance. By modeling the kinematics and coordinating the movements, the system ensures that the three arms can share the same focal plane without interfering with one another [1]. LINC-NIRVANA also adopts a similar philosophy by coordinating the motion of its Star-Enlarger units, using collision-checked guide-star assignments and a structured homing and repositioning sequence to avoid mechanical overlap during multi-star acquisition [2]. The MOONS instrument addresses a different type of challenge: with more than a thousand fiber-positioning units moving at once, its anti-collision strategy continuously evaluates their relative positions and applies geometric checks and interlocks to stop any motion that could lead to a collision [3]. Advanced collision systems, like those in the VLT-FORS, show how PLCs improve safety. These controllers coordinate complex movements, enforce hardware protections, and provide real-time updates on the instrument's status [4]. This shows how modern telescopes integrate algorithms, sensing strategies, and control architectures to manage collision risks in different telescope systems. In the same way, the possible effects of the collision between 2 LOR WFS units during all the phases of the instrument such as science operation and maintenance, servicing or engineering has been evaluated. The outcome has been to introduce risk mitigations on a multi-level strategy to avoid collision and potential damage while on the run. To ensure a safe functionality of MORFEO and to reach the required performance in terms of sky-coverage the LOR WFS Module will implement a collision prevention and mitigation strategy based on two levels.

1.1 Anti-Collision Software (ACS)

A low-level control system developed in TwinCAT and implemented on a PLC. It will continuously monitor the real-time positions (1 ms cycle) and movements of the LOR WFS units to compute safe areas and detect and prevent potential collisions.

1.2 Stop-upon Collision System (SCS)

An electromechanical safety mechanism that cuts power to the motors in the event of physical contact between LOR WFS units. This risk mitigation strategy will operate independently of software control and provide an additional layer of protection against hardware damage. For this purpose, it will use three main components: conductive tapes, mechanical joints and control electronics. This configuration will provide a rapid response in collision scenarios and safety to the component.

2. SOFTWARE

The primary collision avoidance layer is managed by the local PLC software controlling the LOR linear stages. The system converts the astronomical coordinates of the three Natural Guide Stars (NGS) into focal plane coordinates and assigns each NGS to a specific stage. Once assigned, coordinates are mapped to the stage coordinate system, where a pre-positioning anti-collision algorithm is executed.

This algorithm models each stage as a polygonal profile and verifies that no segments intersect or fall within a defined safety threshold. Upon validation, a safe trajectory is commanded to the motors. Simultaneously, a background task continuously monitors real-time stage positions; if a potential collision is detected, the algorithm triggers an emergency stop of all motors within 1ms.

3. HARDWARE

For the SCS application, the 3M ECG7053H conductive tape was selected after evaluating multiple candidates against key criteria including reflectivity, resistivity, adhesion strength, mechanical compliance, and available mounting options. The ECG7053H tape has a nominal thickness of 0.52 ± 0.07 mm and is constructed from a conductive polyurethane foam combined with a conductive pressure-sensitive adhesive. The foam layer provides excellent compressive capability which ensures a stable electrical contact while the adhesive layer offers a peel strength of 500 gf/25 mm (≈ 4.9 N) at 180° , supporting reliable long-term adhesion. To compare optical performance, the reflectance spectra of all candidate tapes were measured using a Filmetrics F20 system over the wavelength range 400–1700 nm, with aluminum used as the standard reference. As shown in fig.3, the 3M ECG7053H tape exhibits reflectance values very close to the baseline across the full spectral bandwidth, indicating extremely low optical reflectance. This characteristic is advantageous for SCS applications where unintended stray reflections should be kept minimal.

Figure 3. The plot shows the reflectivity of all the tape candidates evaluated, here shows the reflectance compared to aluminum.

3.1 SCS Control Electronics

The hardware safety system of the LOR is the SCS (Stop upon Collision System) which has to immediately stop the acquisition stages in case of unwanted collision between the three LOR boards. The SCS tapes will act as a contact sensor that sends a signal to cut-off motor power supply upon collisions. To detect each collision cases, three strips of

conductive tape, each 10 mm in width and spaced 10 mm apart, will be applied to each LOR-WFS board as schematically illustrated in fig.4.

Figure 4. Three layers arrangement of the conductive tape

An industry standard switch amplifier like the KCD2-SR-1.LB by Pepper Fulchs is used to read the dry contacts made by the conductive stripes. The switch amplifier has also the important task to galvanically isolate the input and the output, i.e. the tape from the PLC supply, assuring safe voltages to the WFS board. Since the switch amplifier is designed to read dry contact we must isolate the three conductive stripes while being able to detect each collision case: LOR1-LOR2, LOR2-LOR3, LOR1-LOR3. Also because of this, we will make use of three switch amplifiers and three levels of conductive tapes as previously mentioned. To stop the motor directly without SW operation, the system will cut power to the motor at the supply input of the motor drives through another dedicated safety relay; thus avoiding usual delays of STO lines. It is also important to note that the STO inputs of the motor drives will be reserved for a separate safety mechanism within the LOR system—specifically, the interlock with the SCAO.

Figure 5. SCS and Interlock safety systems of the LOR WFS

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE STEPS

In conclusion, the LOR module of MORFEO implements a multi-layer anti-collision strategy to ensure safe operation of the three NGS wavefront sensing units operating within partially overlapping patrol areas. The proposed architecture combines a real-time Anti-Collision Software (ACS) running on a PLC to prevent unsafe trajectories with an independent hardware-based Stop-upon Collision System (SCS) that rapidly cuts motor power in case of physical contact. The hardware solution, based on conductive tapes, switch amplifiers, and dedicated safety relays, provides an additional layer of protection against potential software failures or unforeseen conditions. Ongoing work focuses on the

finalization and validation of the mechanical protection mechanism integrated in the POM arm, which is designed to tolerate collisions from multiple directions through a preloaded kinematic support system. This design includes sphere–cone and cylinder–V-groove interfaces together with spring and Belleville washer preloads that allow controlled compliance during impact and automatic restoration of the nominal position. Future activities will concentrate on completing the mechanical prototype, performing laboratory validation tests, and integrating the full anti-collision architecture within the MORFEO control system.

Figure 6. Pickoff arm mechanical design: 1) cylinder; 2) cone groove 3) Teflon pad preloaded with a Belleville washer

REFERENCES

- [1] Edward L. Chapin et al., The Infrared Imaging Spectrograph (IRIS) for TMT: motion planning with collision avoidance for the on-instrument wavefront sensors, *Instrumentation and Methods for Astrophysics*, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1608.01681>.
- [2] X. Zhang et al, Natural guide star acquisition for LINC-NIRVANA's MCAO systems. *Optics Express*, 19, 17, 16087 (2011) T. Bertram et al, Multiple guide star acquisition software for LINC-NIRVANA, *Proceedings Volume 8451, Software and Cyberinfrastructure for Astronomy II*; 845126 (2012) <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.926982>
- [3] Van Derlofske, J. F., Development of the fibre positioning unit of MOONS," *Proc SPIE Astronomical Telescopes + Instrumentation*, 2016, Edinburgh, United Kingdom.
- [5] V. Baldini et al, Revamping of VLT-FORS control electronics with PLC systems: the final design *Proceedings Volume 12184, Ground-based and Airborne Instrumentation for Astronomy IX*; 121845G (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2627704>